

Re-translations of the series analysed in the paper “Gender-Fair Audiovisual Translation: First Considerations on How to Address Non-Binary Genders”

Line #	EN	DE	IT	HR
1	PENELOPE: Welcome. What's everybody's name?	Willkommen. Wie heißt ihr?	Benvenute. Come vi chiamate?	Drago mi je. Kako se zovete?
2	DANI: I'm Dani. My pronouns are she and her.	Ich bin Dani. Meine Pronomen sind „sie“ und „ihr“.	Io Dani. I miei pronomi sono “lei” e “le”.	Dani. Moje zamjenice su “ona” i “njoj”.
3	SYD: I'm Syd, my pronouns are they and them.	Ich heiÙe Syd, meine Pronomen sind „dey“ und „denen“.	Syd. Non uso pronomi di genere.	Syd. Zamjenice “on/ona” i “njemu/njoj”.
4	MARGAUX: I'm Margaux, pronouns ze and zir.	Ich bin Margaux, ich verwende die Pronomen „xier“ und „xiem“.	Margaux. Uso qualsiasi pronome.	Margaux, zamjenice “ze” i “zir”.
5	PENELOPE: I'm Penelope, my thoughts are huh and what? Seriously, what is happening?	Penelope. Meine Gedanken sind “Hä?” und “Was?” Im Ernst, was geht hier vor sich?	Sono Penelope e penso: “pronomi di genere?” Sul serio, che sta succedendo?	Ja sam Penelope, a misli su mi “Ùto?” i “kako?” Zbilja, Ùto se ovdje dogaða?
6	ELENA: Well, because some people are gender non-conforming, they have certain preferred pronouns.	Also, manche Menschen sind gender-nonkonform, und sprechen daher ihre Pronomen aus.	Siccome esistono persone di genere non conforme, usano o meno diversi pronomi.	Neke osobe koriste zamjenice na drugaçiji naçin, pa ih iz tog razloga izgovaraju.

7	LYDIA: Ah, I am Lydia. Pronounced "Lee-dee-ah."	Ah, mein Name ist Lydia. Aussprache „Ly-di-a“.	Ah, io mi chiamo Lydia. Genere non comunista.	Ja sam Lydia, a izgovara se: "Li-di-ja".
---	---	---	--	---

Table 1. One Day At A Time: our re-translations

Line #	EN	DE	IT	HR
1	MICHAEL (teacher): What's going on?	Was ist los?	Che succede?	Što se događa?
2	TEACHER2: Cal Bowman's been missing since last night. That's their mom.	Cal Bowman wird seit gestern Abend vermisst. Das ist deren Mutter.	Cal Bowman manca da casa da ieri sera. Quella è la madre.	Cal Bowman nema od sinoć. Ono im je mama.
3	MICHAEL: God, that's awful.	Mensch, das ist ja furchtbar.	Diamine, è terribile.	Isuse, to je grozno.
4	STUDENT 1: Yeah, yeah. We'll make sure there's people searching the skate park.	Ja. Wir lassen Leute den Skatepark durchsuchen.	Ci assicureremo che qualcuno vada allo skate park.	Da. Pobrinut ćemo se da ljudi pretraže <i>skate</i> park.
5	STUDENT 2: Thank your for coming, everyone. Cal is in a very vulnerable place right now, so we need to start searching for them straight away.	Danke, dass ihr gekommen seid. Cal ist derzeit in einem labilen Zustand, also müssen wir sofort nach denen suchen.	Grazie a tutto per essere venut o . // Grazie di cuore per essere qui. Cal è molto vulnerabile in questo momento. Quindi dobbiamo iniziare le ricerche immediatamente.	Hvala svima što ste došli. Cal je trenutačno u osjetljivoj situaciji pa ih moramo odmah početi tražiti.

6	STUDENT 1: Their last text message said they were going to Pinelands Shopping Center.	Laut letzter Nachricht wollte dey ins Pinelands Einkaufszentrum.	Nell'ultimo messaggio ha detto che si trovava al centro commerciale Pinelands.	Cal napisa da ide u trgovački centar Pinelands.
---	--	---	---	---

Table 2. Sex Education: our re-translations

Line #	EN	DE	HR
1	STEPFATHER: You're around tonight?	Du bist abends hier, oder?	Večeras si kod kuće?
2	DARREN: Why?	Wieso?	Zašto?
3	STEPFATHER: Nothing, just the boys are coming over to watch the game, is all.	Nichts, nur, die Jungs kommen, um das Spiel anzusehen, das ist alles.	Dolaze dečki gledati utakmicu.
4	DARREN: Mmmm. Okay, and you want me to not be around?	Ok, und du willst, dass ich hier nicht rumhänge?	I želite da ne budem kod kuće?
5	STEPFATHER: He always assumes the worst.	Ha! Er geht immer vom Schlimmsten aus.	On uvijek pretpostavlja najgore.
6	MOTHER: They, they.	Sier, sier!	Ne kaži "on".
7	DARREN: They! They always assume the worst.	Sier! Sier geht immer vom Schlimmsten aus.	Da, ne koristim zamjenice muškog roda.

8	STEPFATHER: This again. I mean, it's exactly my point. My mates can't be expected to get their heads around this stuff.	Das schon wieder. Ich meine... das ist genau mein Punkt. Meine Kumpels können diese Sachen nicht verstehen.	Opet ovo. Upravo je u tome stvar. Moji frendovi ne mogu shvatiti takve stvari.
9	DARREN: Sorry, what stuff?	Sorry, welche Sachen?	Oprosti, koje stvari?
10	STEPFATHER: The linguistics. "Them." "They." It doesn't make any sense. You know you're not two people, right?	Die Linguistik. Sier ergibt keinen Sinn. Du weißt, dass du nicht beides sein kannst.	Lingvističke. Ne mogu reći "ono". To nema smisla. (To isto krši gramatička pravila.)

Table 3. Heartbreak High: Our re-translation

Line #	EN	DE	IT	HR
1	LOLA: My favourite vlogger did a thing about this. They identify as genderqueer. Or, I think there's a name for it. Uhm... genderfluid. They feel like they're between a boy or girl. Or both. Or neither. Does that make sense?	Mein*e Lieblingsvlogger*in machte etwas zu dem Thema. Xier definiert sich als "genderqueer". Oder es heißt auch "genderfluid". Xier fühlt sich zwischen Junge und Mädchen. Oder beides. Oder nichts davon. Ergibt das irgendwie Sinn?	Le miə vlogger preferite ne parla.// Una persona con un vlog ne parla// Il mio vlog preferito ne parla. Si identifica come genderqueer. Ah, usa un'altra definizione... genderfluid. Sente di essere a metà tra i due generi. O entrambi. O nessuno dei due. - Ha senso per te?	Moja najomiljenija osoba koja snima vlogove govori o tome. Identificira se kao "genderqueer" osoba. A možda se i kaže rodno fluidna osoba. Osjeća se kao osoba između ženskog i muškog roda. Ili kao osoba oba, ili nijednog roda. Ima li to smisla?

2	YAEL: No.	Nein	- No.	Ne.
3	LOLA: Okay, it's like... if being a boy or a girl is made up, then you can be whatever you want, right? There, that's them.	Ok, also... Wenn die Kategorien Junge und Mädchen ein erfundenes Konstrukt sind, kann man sein, was man will, oder? Hier, das ist xier .	Allora, immagina... Che definire i generi non abbia senso. Tu puoi essere come vuoi, chiaro? Ecco/Eccola , guarda. (a single person is shown)	Ovako... Ako su ženski i muški rod izmišljeni, onda možeš biti što god želiš. Nije li tako? O ovoj osobi govorim.

Table 4. Degrassi: our re-translations